

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF COMPOSITE BOLTED JOINTS REPAIRED WITH INSERTS

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Keywords: *composite joints, countersunk bolts, fasteners, repair, insert, fem, testing*

1 Introduction

Bolted joints have been extensively used on aircraft since the dawn of aviation and, even with the recent and widespread introduction of composite materials, still play a key role in aeronautical structures. Along with high strength and versatility, this technology offers the possibility to disassemble the joint for inspection and maintenance or to access concealed parts of the structure.

During the manufacturing of structures, errors can occur. If the structure is expensive, it is economically and environmentally important to attempt a repair with the aim of restoring the designed mechanical performance. A particular error that can occur in the production of aeronautical structures, such as a wing or fuselage, is the slight misplacement of drilled holes in a bolted connection between large composite plates. Such errors can be repaired through the use of metallic inserts.

This paper presents a finite element (FE) and experimental investigation of the static mechanical behaviour of single-lap composite joints, with countersunk bolts, repaired with metallic inserts. The FE model has been used to help interpret the results obtained from the experiments.

2 Literature Review

Limited literature can be found on the use of inserts as a repair technique in composite fastened joints. Previous studies focused on the introduction of bonded inserts to increase the bearing strength of fastened joints. Camanho and Matthews [1] investigated the use of bonded metallic inserts to improve the strength of double-lap composite bolted joints. It was found that bonded metallic inserts reduced the stress concentrations in the vicinity of the hole. Nevertheless, the failure of the adhesive took place far before the ultimate load of the joint, hence, providing little improvement. Camanho et al. [2] found that the development of damage was delayed using bonded inserts due to the new regions

of load transfer that were created. Bonded inserts were able to transfer the load to the laminate through the whole surface of the hole instead of approximately half the hole surface. However, after the failure of the adhesive, the stresses were not relieved anymore and the laminate exhibited composite bearing failure.

Mazraehshahi et al. [3] focused their study on the influence of the geometry of the insert on the stress field of composite plates. The effects of different thicknesses, clearances and materials were studied by means of a three-dimensional finite element model. They concluded that increasing clearances lead to higher radial stresses. In addition, the reduction of stress concentrations when using thicker inserts was confirmed by this study.

3 Investigated Configurations

The analysed configurations consisted of single-lap joints made of unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) plates, titanium countersunk bolts and steel nuts, tested under tensile loading. The single-lap joint configurations consisted of two bolts contrary placed, with the fastener heads on different sides of the joint as shown in Fig. 1. Two different composite plate thicknesses and two different bolt reference configurations were used per each thickness, named *standard* and *swapped*. In the *standard* single-lap joint configuration, the countersunk heads of the bolts were placed towards the run-out of the plates (critical location for shear-out failure; Figs 1 and 3). On the contrary, in the *swapped* single-lap joint configuration, the countersunk heads of the bolts were placed in the internal holes of the plates (critical location for net-section failure; Fig. 2). Two support composite plates were also bonded to the main plates of the joint to avoid any eccentricity in the application of the external tensile load. The stacking sequence of the CFRP plates was $[\pm 45/0/90/\mp 45/0/90]_S$ and $[(\pm 45/0/90/\mp 45/0/90)_2]_S$ for the thin and thick

specimens, respectively. Thus, both thin and thick laminates consisted of 50% of $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, 25% of 0° plies and 25% of 90° . The ply thickness of the material used was nominally 0.187mm [4], yielding a nominal laminate thickness after curing of ~ 3 mm and ~ 6 mm. Bolt types EN6114K4-4 and EN6114K4-8 were used. The bolts for both thin and thick configurations had identical diameter (6.35 mm; (1/4")) and countersunk head but different shank length. In all the configurations, nut type ASNA2536-4 was used and the repair inserts were made of aluminium. The investigated configurations were:

- reference joints; without insert, designed to have bearing/fastener failure (Fig. 1). Two swapped and two standard joint configurations for both composite plate thicknesses were studied (i.e. a total of four different configurations);
- joints with coaxial (symmetric) inserts; an aluminium insert with coaxial internal and external profiles was located around a countersunk bolt head. This is a repair technique for a joint with a hole drilled in the correct position but with an oversized diameter. The cases of inserts with wall thicknesses of 1.07 and 3.32 mm were studied (Fig. 2) and for both the thin and thick composite plates (i.e. a total of four different configurations). Coaxial inserts were placed at the internal hole of the joint in order to study possible net-tension failures. Thus the *swapped* joint configuration was used for all the coaxial inserts;
- joints with non-coaxial (asymmetric) inserts; an aluminium insert with non-coaxial internal and external profiles was located around a countersunk head. This is a repair technique for a joint with axis of a drilled hole not positioned in the correct location. Three cases were studied for both thin and thick composite plates (i.e. a total of 6 different configurations). The inserts were positioned towards the run-out (Fig. 3), towards the other bolt and towards the side of the composite plate. Non-coaxial inserts were placed close to the run-out to investigate possible shear out failures. Thus the *standard* joint configuration was used for all the non-coaxial inserts.

3.1 Nomenclature

A numerical code allows a fast identification of the configuration and an alphabetical code provides a full description of the sample. The alphabetical code

is based on abbreviations that indicate the position of the bolts (standard or swapped), the thickness of the composite plates, the size and type of the insert and the positioning for the non-coaxial inserts (Table 1). A complete list of the specimens under investigation is presented in Table 2, which relates the numerical and alphabetical codes. The different insert configurations used are illustrated in Fig 4.

4 Finite Element Investigation

Highly-detailed, three-dimensional, non-linear finite-element models of composite bolted joints repaired with metallic inserts (Fig. 5) were developed with the finite element software Abaqus 6.10, based on the work published by Stocchi et al. [5].

A three-dimensional model was required to study the joint behaviour due to the three dimensional stress state introduced by the preload, the hole edge stresses and the secondary bending [6]. In order to provide a time-effective means of evaluating the repaired joint behaviour, a script was coded in Python to automatically generate the FE models for the desired configurations.

The mesh density and the element refinement were found as the best compromise between convergence, accuracy and computational cost (Fig. 5). The model is able to account for the effect of the clearances between the bolt, the insert and the composite plates (Fig. 6).

The material modelling comprised of an elasto-plastic behaviour for the metallic materials and orthotropic elastic behaviour for the CFRP. A full definition of all the contacts between the plates, the bolts and the insert was implemented. The FE model was validated against the results obtained during the experimental program. The analysis has a dynamic-implicit formulation and was divided in two steps:

1. the clamping force was applied to the bolts using the Bolt Load keyword, which shrinks the length of the shank to introduce the desired preload.
2. grips were simulated by two rigid bodies located at the edges of the model and associated with two reference points. The tensile load was applied imposing a linear displacement to one of these points whereas the other was kept fixed.

Several parametric studies were conducted to investigate the effect of the hole-insert-bolt clearances and of the height of the insert on the joint mechanical behaviour.

5 Experimental Procedure

5.1 Specimen Manufacture

The two different thicknesses of the quasi-isotropic laminates were manufactured and cured according to the prepreg manufacturer recommended procedure. Once manufactured, all the panels were ultrasonically (C-scan) tested in order to ensure that no defects were present (e.g. delaminations, inclusions, voids). The support plates were bonded to the main plates using FM300 film adhesive. Before bonding, the surfaces were sand-blasted and cleaned. The specimens were obtained by dry-cutting the panels into strips with a nominal width of 50.8 mm and the holes were drilled using tungsten carbide drills.

The accurate positioning of the insert in the joint was of paramount importance in order to correctly evaluate the behaviour of the joint with the insert. Therefore, great care was given to the positioning of the insert into the hole. In all the joint configurations, the length of the insert was adjusted (by abrading the lower surface), so that it was 0.2 mm shorter than the thickness of the composite plate. All bolts were tightened with a torque of 7.4 Nm. Fig. 7 shows an assembled specimen with a non-coaxial insert located towards the run-out of the plate. Two specimens were manufactured for each investigated configurations mentioned in section 3.

5.2 Tensile Testing

Static tensile tests were performed on two specimens for each configuration (Fig. 8). A test machine (Instron 4505) was used to perform the tensile tests, using a 100 kN load cell. A fixed displacement rate of 1 mm/min was used for all the tests.

The specimens were tested until final failure, passing through a partial unload-reload loop. The thin and thick specimens were loaded up to 18 kN and 27 kN, respectively, then unloaded to 10 kN and finally re-loaded to failure. The load and displacement readings were taken from the machine load cell and LVDTs, respectively (Fig. 8).

5.3 Non Destructive Evaluation

In addition to visual observation, a post-failure analysis of the failure of the specimens was conducted, using X-Rays. Since the X-Ray linear absorption coefficient of CFRP is relatively low, an opaque organic X-Ray penetrant (dibromomethane) was used to highlight the damage in the vicinity of the holes. Each specimen was immersed in the

penetrant for 2 min (contact time) and left to dry for 20 mins (dwell time) before being X-Ray tested.

6 Results and Discussion

6.1 Stages in Load-Displacement Behaviour

Both the FE investigation and the experimental program highlighted five stages in the behaviour of the repaired composite joints, as observed by Stocchi et al. [5] for joints without inserts. The stages were (i) No-Slip, (ii) Slip, (iii) Full Contact, (iv) Damage and (v) Final Failure. The different stages can be clearly identified in the sample load-displacement curve of the test 3.6/1 st-tk-L-asym-sd (Fig. 9).

In the No-slip stage, the joint exhibits the highest stiffness of the five stages. Stocchi et al. [5] showed that, in the No-slip stage, the load is fully transferred through friction. In this stage the shank of the bolt is not in contact with the plate or the straight surface of the insert and no relative movement between the plates occurs. Therefore, the stiffness of the joint depends on the stiffness of the CFRP plates. It can be seen from the Load-Displacement graph (Fig. 10) that the length of this stage was approximately the same for reference and repaired joints.

The Slip stage starts when the external force exceeds the maximum load that can be transferred only through friction between the plates. From this point forward, the plates start to slip and the clearance between holes and bolts is progressively reduced. There is no significant increase in the carried load and a substantial drop in the stiffness occurs. The length of the Slip stage is therefore linked to the amount of clearance present in the joint. This is in full accordance with the numerical and experimental work of McCarthy et al. [7, 8] and Stocchi et al. [5]. The smooth stiffness transition between the Slip and the Full Contact stage is due to the progressively increasing contact between the bolt, insert and hole. The straight holes of the plate are usually the first to come in contact with the shank of the bolt, followed by the contact of the straight portion of the countersunk hole with the straight surface of the insert. The order of the contact sequence depends on the relative clearances between the plate, insert and bolt.

In the Full Contact stage the majority of the load is transferred through the contact between the shank of the bolts and the straight portion of the holes and the inserts. The local compliance of the aforementioned

contact leads to lower stiffness compared to the No-Slip stage.

The Damage stage is characterised by a progressive loss of stiffness caused by the metallic components undergoing extensive yielding together with the onset and propagation of bearing damage in the composite plates.

Eventually, Final Failure stage results in a sudden drop in the load carried by the joint. The failure can be attributed to a single failure mode such as bolt head failure or to a combination of different failure modes.

6.2 Numerical Results: Bolt/Insert Failures and Parametric Studies

High concentration of stress and plastic strain was found at the fillets of the bolt head and insert, and at the straight contact area of the latter. The application of the 10 kN bolt preload appears to be enough to plasticise extensively the insert and to cause a more localised yielding of the bolts. The yielding subsequently progresses to the straight portion of the insert with the application of the tensile loading. The bolt shank section at the height of the faying surface also exhibited extensive plastic strain due to high shear stresses.

The numerical results indicated that the configurations with inserts exhibit a similar response to the reference configurations. Thin configurations showed lower stiffness than reference ones in the Full-Contact phase probably due to the extensive yielding of the inserts that was also observed during the experimental program. The joints with non-coaxial inserts did not exhibit a different behaviour except for the 3.5 st-tn-L-asym-sd configuration samples with non-coaxial inserts which exhibited a softening phase larger than expected (Fig. 11). This behaviour was also present during the testing of the samples and it seems that it could have been caused by the rotation of the insert around its external profile axis, due to the moment generated by the resultant forces of the bolt and plate on the insert (Fig. 12). The rotation of the insert was limited by the friction forces and the presence of the bolt.

A parametric study was performed in order to assess the impact of the height of the insert on the preload distribution due to the reduction of the distance between the insert and the lower plate when the preload is applied (Fig. 13). The analyses were performed using the 3.1 st-tn-L-asym-out configuration. A first FE analysis was carried out with a 0.3 mm gap between the bottom end of the insert and the opposite composite plate so that no

contact between the insert and plate could occur. Subsequently, the 3.1 st-tn-L-asym-out configuration was analysed with no gap between the insert and the lower plate. The numerical results showed that the configurations had similar responses and that the No-Slip and Slip phases were clearly defined in both configurations. Therefore, when no gap was present, the preload compressed the insert against the lower plate and the friction between the insert and the lower plate was responsible for the No-Slip phase (Fig. 14). Hence, the height of the insert did not have a noticeable impact in load response of the joint for this specific type of insert repair and similar coefficients of friction between both plates and between the insert and the bottom plate.

Clearances are known to play an important role in the distribution of the load in multi-bolt composite joints [9]. Therefore, the influence of the clearances on the joints with inserts was investigated using the parametric capabilities of the FEM model. Two different scenarios were studied for the 3.3 st-tn-L-asym-in. Clearances of 0.2 mm and 0.3 mm between the insert and the plate were considered. First, maintaining at 0.05 mm the clearances at the other bolt and, second, by having at the other bolt the same clearance of the insert (i.e. 0.2 mm and 0.3 mm). The results showed that a clear sliding phase was present for the second scenario whereas almost no clearance was found in the response behaviour for the first scenario (Figs 15 and 16). The results also showed that contact stresses increased in both scenarios in comparison with the nominal 3.3 st-tn-L-asym-sd configuration with a clearance of 0.09 mm in the insert. For a tensile load of 15 kN, the contact stresses increased by 8% and 31% for the first and second scenarios respectively with a gap of 0.3 mm.

Since the clearances at the insert for the first scenario were around four to six times the clearances at the bolt, contact occurred at the bolt with no insert far earlier than for the one with the insert, showing a response with a short sliding phase and a moderate increase of the stresses due to the unequal sharing of the load, which is in line with previous studies on clearances [7]. For the second scenario, since insert and bolt had large clearances, both plates had to slide further until Full-Contact was achieved, resulting in a considerably longer sliding phase and a consequent loss of stiffness. Higher clearances reduced the bolt-plate contact area [5, 8], partially leading to an increase of 31% in the contact stresses. In addition, higher clearances resulted in further

indentation of the bolts due to larger secondary bending [10].

6.3 Experimental Results on Bolt/Insert Failures

6.3.1 Joint behaviour

Load versus Displacement graphs were obtained from all the tests. The displacements were calculated from the LVDTs (Fig. 8).

The test machine cross head displacement was significantly larger than the displacement determined from the LVDT readings due to the compliance of the machine.

6.3.2 Unload-Reload loop

The unload-reload loops were characterised by a joint stiffness similar to the No-Slip stage. The stiffness increase with respect to the Full-Contact stage is due to the friction between the two plates which limits the relative movement of the plates. As for the No-Slip stage, in the unload-reload loop the change in the load is mainly transferred by friction. Therefore, the different paths followed by the unload-reload loop can be attributed to the limited amount of slip between the plates. The area between the load paths represents the energy dissipation due to friction. Finally, the limited plate movement results in the initial and final points of the unload-reload loop being nearly coincident.

6.3.3 Maximum Load Comparison

The average maximum load for the *standard* and *swapped* thin reference joint configurations were 32% and 35% lower than the corresponding thick joints. Therefore, the average tensile stresses reached in the thin composite specimens were on average 36% and 30% higher than for the thick specimens of the *standard* and *swapped* configurations, respectively. Hence, the thin specimens exhibited better efficiency than the corresponding thick ones.

However, the failure modes found for both thick and thin reference configurations were bolt head failure instead of composite failure, and therefore, the thin specimens, although more efficient, led to bolt failure for lower tensile loads than the thick specimens.

This premature bolt head failure found for the thin specimens can be explained by the larger secondary bending suffered by the thin specimens, which resulted in a greater tilting of the bolts inside the holes. Taking a closer look at the bolt head failure present for all the reference samples (except for 1.1/1 st-tn-Ref, where bolt pull through failure

occurred), it was concluded that the head failure occurred when cracks propagated upwards from the fillet of the countersunk head (Fig. 17). This bolt head failure is driven by the forces acting on the countersunk head of the bolt. In thick specimens, stresses were more evenly distributed along the area of contact between the bolt and the composite plate. On the contrary, in thin specimens, the larger tilting of bolts reduced the area of contact at the shank, increasing the contact stresses at the head and the fillet of the bolt, and thus, leading to the premature failure of the bolts.

Small differences in the strength were generally found between configurations with inserts and their respective reference configurations. Figs 18-21 show the average maximum load for all the configurations under study. The range of each error bar shows the two load values obtained for the two tested specimens for each configuration. Error bars are not available for configurations 3.3 st-tn-L-asym-in, 3.5 st-tn-L-asym-sd, 3.2 st-tk-L-asym-out and 3.6 st-tk-L-asym-sd, since only one specimen was tested for these configurations. The numbers in brackets inside the bars of Figs 18-21 refer to the percentage difference between the average maximum load obtained for the specific configuration with the insert and for the corresponding reference joint. The largest difference in strength was observed for the thin plate specimen of 3.5 st-tn-L-asym-sd configuration, which exhibited a maximum load of 15% lower than the 1.3 st-tn-Ref reference joint (Fig. 20). The rest of the configurations showed consistent results between reference and repaired joints with the average maximum loads fluctuating between -6% and +7% compared with the reference configurations. Even if the difference was generally limited, 2.2 st-tk-S-sym (Fig. 19) and 2.3 sw-tn-L-sym (Fig. 18) were the only configurations with inserts that showed an improvement on the maximum load. Configurations 3.1 st-tn-L-asym-out (Fig. 20) and 3.6 st-tk-L-asym-sd (Fig. 21) exhibited almost no difference in the maximum load compared to their respective reference configurations.

The results generally showed that the composite bolted joints with inserts have similar strength to the joints without inserts. This is because the maximum load was mostly dependent on the strength of the bolt rather than on the strength of the laminate or the insert. Bearing damage and plasticisation of the insert led to higher maximum displacements but did not directly cause the final failure of the joint. This conclusion is in agreement with the tests on

composite bolted joints without inserts performed by McCarthy et al. [7], where although the bearing damage was the primary failure mode, the ultimate joint failure was bolt head failure.

6.3.4 Failure Observation

6.3.4.1 Visual Observation

As aforementioned, the dominant failure mode in the tests performed was bolt head failure (Fig. 17). Neither net-section, nor shear-out failures occurred in the tested specimens. The specimens showed secondary bending along their length when loaded due to the anti-symmetry of the joints. This effect was particularly obvious for the thin specimens due to their lower bending stiffness. As a result, tilting of the bolts into the holes occurred, which led to a combination of bolt pull through failure and bolt head failure (Fig. 22). However, only 1.1/1 sw-tn and 3.1/1 st-tn-L-asym-out specimens exhibited pure bolt pull through failure (Fig. 23).

It was found that failure occurred mostly in the bolt without the insert. This might be caused by the unequal load sharing at the two bolts due to the extensive yielding of the insert (Fig. 24, test 2.1/2 sw-tn-S-sym). This phenomenon was accompanied with hole elongation and it was more extensive in the thin specimens than in the thick ones (Fig. 25). Furthermore, insert tilting was observed to induce surface damage. The worn region that is illustrated in Fig. 26 (Hole 1) was the result of the matrix being smeared out due to the contact with the insert.

Further damage was observed at the faying surface of the composite plates in the vicinity of the holes for the thin specimens. Cracks were observed in the direction of the fibres of the external ply for both specimens of test 2.3 sw-tn-L-sym, (Fig. 26; Hole 2 of the composite plate). In the majority of the thick specimens, limited damage was visually observed in the composite plates.

Extensive bearing damage was found in the thin configurations while the thick configurations exhibited almost no presence of bearing damage (Fig. 27). The following equation [11] was employed in order to calculate the load that would trigger bearing damage for thick specimens.

$$S_b = \frac{P_b}{dt} \quad (1)$$

where S_b is the bearing stress, P_b is the bearing load, d is the diameter of the hole and t is the thickness of the plate.

Since the numerical models presented in this paper did not account for bearing damage, the knee in the

experimental load-displacement curve was considered as the bearing damage initiation load. Thus, it can be seen from test 1.3 st-tn-Ref (Fig. 28) that the onset of bearing damage for thin specimens occurred around 16.5 kN. This leads to an initiation of bearing damage at a stress around 866 MPa according to equation 1. Following the same approach, for thick specimens the external load would have to reach 33 kN to trigger the initiation of bearing damage. Little or no bearing damage was found for thick specimens since bolt head failure generally occurred at loads slightly lower than 33 kN and hence, before significant bearing damage could develop in the thick specimens.

Likewise, the inserts installed in the thick configurations suffered significantly less damage compared to the inserts used in the thin configurations (Fig. 27).

6.3.4.2 X-Ray Observation

X-Rays were used for the post failure analysis of some of the thin specimens. The image processing techniques that were used gave a clear image of the fracture surfaces and of the extent of the damage on the specimens. The length of the bearing damage is clearly illustrated in the X-Rays images (Fig. 29). Delamination was observed near the holes in some specimens, (Fig. 29) being depicted in the picture by a dark shadow around the hole. The delamination was found to be localised opposite to the hole face where bearing occurred and also in the countersunk hole of the plate. The tilting of the bolt into the hole led to the abrading of the composite plies by the countersunk head of the bolt which probably caused the initiation of delamination in this region of the hole.

In addition, the damage observed on the surface around the hole edges was most likely to be caused by the drilling procedure, which is in line with similar observations made by Starikov and Schön [12].

6.4 Comparison of Finite element and Experimental results

The numerical and experimental Load-Displacement curves were in good agreement for the No-Slip, Slip and Full contact stages as well as for the unload-reload loop.

However, for the Damage stage, the actual response of the joint differed from the numerical simulations. This is because the model employed only accounted for the softening introduced by the plasticisation of

the metallic insert and bolts, but no bearing damage in the composite plate was considered.

The differences found in the Slip stage were likely to be attributed to the variation in the manufactured clearances, while the differences in the Full-Contact phase were mainly determined by the limits of the yielding model used for the inserts.

7 Conclusions

A finite-element and experimental investigation of single-lap composite joints with countersunk bolts, repaired with different types of metallic inserts under static tensile load was presented.

Five stages were identified in the joint behaviour with inserts. These were (i) No-Slip, (ii) Slip, (iii) Full Contact, (iv) Damage and (v) Final Failure.

Bolt head failure was the dominant failure mode observed for all the joints. The experimental results showed that the inserts under study did not trigger any shear out or net tension failure of the joints.

The analysis of the experimental load-displacement response suggested that the use of asymmetric inserts led to a slightly lower stiffness in the Slip and the Full Contact stages which is in agreement with the behaviour predicted by the numerical simulations.

According to the experimental results, the strength of the repaired composite joints did not exhibit significant variations compared to the reference samples without inserts.

The post failure analysis showed extensive bearing damage in the thin composite plates as well as massive yielding of the inserts. In contrast, thick specimens did not exhibit significant bearing damage since bolt head failure occurred first.

The parametric studies performed with the FE model showed that the clearances between the inserts and the plate had a great impact on the stress state of the joint, directly affecting the load distribution between the bolts.

The experimental study concluded that the repaired joints performed as well as the non-repaired ones only with a slight reduction of stiffness.

The FE model was able to capture the key stages in the behaviour and to identify the critical points in the joints, providing a valuable insight into the joint response.

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Table. 1. Alphabetical code used for the designation of the different configurations.

Swapped/Standard	sw	Swapped bolts configuration (Net tension failure check)
	st	Standard bolts configuration (Shear out failure check)
Plate thickness	tn	Thin plate specimen
	tk	Thick plate specimen
Insert size (external diameter)	S	Small insert
	L	Large insert
Insert symmetry	sym	Coaxial (symmetric) insert
	asym	Non-coaxial (asymmetric) insert
Asymmetry direction	in	Towards the inner bolt
	out	Towards the run out of the plate
	sd	Towards one side of the plate

Table. 2. Numerical code used for the fourteen different configurations under investigation.

Reference specimens		Net tension specimens		Shear out specimens	
No	Code	No	Code	No	Code
1.1	sw-tn	2.1	sw-tn-S-sym	3.1	st-tn-L-asym-out
1.2	sw-tk	2.2	sw-tk-S-sym	3.2	st-tk-L-asym-out
1.3	st-tn	2.3	sw-tn-L-sym	3.3	st-tn-L-asym-in
1.4	st-tk	2.4	sw-tk-L-sym	3.4	st-tk-L-asym-in
				3.5	st-tn-L-asym-sd
				3.6	st-tk-L-asym-sd

Fig. 1. Reference composite bolted joint configuration with no insert and the countersunk head towards the run out.

Fig. 2. Coaxial (symmetric) insert placed in the net section critical location with the countersunk head towards the gripping area.

Fig. 3. Non-Coaxial (asymmetric) insert placed in the shear out critical location towards the run out of the plate.

Fig. 4. Inserts implemented in the repaired composite bolted joints under investigation.

Fig. 5. Section of a FE model of a composite bolted joint with a non-coaxial insert oriented towards the run-out (3.1 configuration).

Fig. 6. Detail of the insert clearances implemented during the meshing strategy for the 3.1 configuration.

Fig. 7. Composite bolted joint with non-coaxial insert towards the run-out of the plate.

Fig. 8. Experimental set-up for the tensile test of the bolted joint.

Fig. 9. Five stages in the behaviour of a joint with an insert.

Fig. 10. Comparison of Load-Displacement curves between thin specimens of standard configuration and non-coaxial inserts moved towards the run out of the plate.

Fig. 11. Load-displacement response comparison between reference and 3.5 st-tn-L-asym-sd non-coaxial insert configuration.

Fig. 12. Rotation of the insert for 3.5 configuration under a 9 kN joint tensile load, left, and the resultant pair of forces, right.

Fig. 13. Distance reduction between the countersunk insert and the lower plate after the preload.

Fig. 14. Preload path with gap, left, and without it, right.

Fig. 15. Insert clearance influence in the load response behaviour for bolted joints under the first clearance scenario, 3.3 st-tn-L-asym-in configuration.

Fig. 16. Insert clearance influence in the load response behaviour for bolted joints under the second clearance scenario, 3.3 st-tn-L-asym-in configuration.

Fig. 17. Bolt head failure.

Fig. 18. Maximum load comparison between tests 1.1 (sw-tn-Ref), 2.1 (sw-tn-S-sym) and 2.3 (sw-tn-L-sym).

Fig. 19. Maximum load comparison between tests 1.2 (sw-tk-Ref), 2.2 (sw-tk-S-sym) and 2.4 (sw-tk-L-sym).

Fig. 20. Maximum load comparison between tests 1.3 (st-tn-Ref), 3.1 (st-tn-L-asym-out), 3.3 (st-tn-L-asym-in) and 3.5 (st-tn-L-asym-sd).

Fig. 21. Maximum load comparison between tests 1.4 (st-tk-Ref), 3.2 (st-tk-L-asym-out), 3.4 (st-tk-L-asym-in) and 3.6 (st-tk-L-asym-sd).

Fig. 22. Combination of bolt head failure and bolt pull through failure, test 2.3/2 sw-tn-L-sym.

Fig. 23. Bolt pull through failure, test 1.1/1 sw-tn-Ref.

Fig. 24. Tilting of the bolt in the insert, test 2.1/2 sw-tn-S-sym.

Fig. 25. Plasticisation of the insert for thin (Test 2.1/1 sw-tk-S-sym), right, and thick (Test 2.2/2 sw-tk-S-sym), left.

Fig. 26. Surface damage due to the contact with the insert (Hole 1) and cracks in the direction of the fibres (Hole 2), test 2.3/2 sw-tn-L-sym.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 27. Difference in the extension of bearing damage for thin and thick composite plates from the same joint configuration. (a) test 2.3/2 sw-tn-L-sym Plate A, (b) test 2.4/2 Plate A sw-tk-L-sym, (c) test 2.3/2 Plate B, (d) test 2.4/2 Plate B.

Fig. 28. Comparison between experimental and numerical Load-Displacement curves, test 1.3 st-tn-Ref.

Fig. 29. X-Rays applied on Plate A from test 1.1/1 sw-tn-Ref.